

The Research on The Impact of Changes in Human Resource Management Components on Employee Stress.

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Abstract – Stress in the workplace is a phenomenon known worldwide for the considerable challenge it presents to employers, as well as for the significant consequences it has on the safety, health and well-being of employees. It is important for managers and employees to understand that even though they cannot clearly see the stressful factors, it does not mean that they cannot cause health consequences.

Therefore, all institutions or enterprises must take measures to reduce the factors and situations that induce high levels of stress.

This thesis aims to analyze the impact of changes in human resource management (HRM) components on employee's stress. Human Resource Management is an advanced and innovative platform for identifying and solving dynamic employee issues, as its components are designed for employee's well-being.

The results show that transparency and fairness in recruitment and selection processes are essential in reducing stress. Effective training and development programs enhance employee's skills and confidence, reducing work-related stress. Clear and objective performance evaluation systems help alleviate performance-related stress. Furthermore, fair and competitive reward and benefit systems are closely linked to reducing stress and increasing employee's motivation. A supportive and positive work environment, influenced by good relationships between employees and supervisors, is key to employee well-being.

Keywords – Management, Human Resources, Stress, Employee.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Resource Management plays a very important role in the employees' wellbeing (Alonso, L. and Elovainio, M., 2022; Alam et, al., 2020), especially regarding work-related stress (Bharathi T and Gupta K.S.,2017; Datt, Dr., Punam and Washington, Dr., Anthea, 2015). Changes that have been made in the recruitment practices, training process and carrier development are closely related to the employees' stress and productivity (Eades, J., 2014; Kirkpatrick, D., & Kirkpatrick, J., 2016; Adeyemi, J. K., 2022). The way that these changes are managed strongly effects the performance and wellbeing in the workplace.

The aim of this study is to analyse the connection between the changes made in the HRM practices and their effect on the employees' stress in the Municipality of Korca. By analysing the key components such as recruitment, training, development, compensation and the relationships between employees, this study aim to give valuable recommendations, in order to help managers to create a healthy and productive work environment.

Through a detailed systematic review and empiric study, based on questionnaires filled in by employees of the Municipality of Korca, this study aims to discover the main factors that cause stress and how to reduce them.

A wide variety of studies, including classic and modern literature, secondary data and other academic resources have helped in this analysis.

More specifically, the theory is based on well-documented resources of HRM field, including work-related stress management theories, the effect of management style, HR policies and effective supervision. These resources have served to create a stable theory, based on evidence.

Secondary data, which is a very important resource in this study, has been gathered by a variety of reliable resources, such as scientific articles, research, studies made by different organisations and academic literature, written by known experts of the management and work psychology field. This information has been used to complete the data gathered from the questionnaires and has provided a wide perspective about work-related stress.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The methodology used in this study holds a special place. During the first phase, we have selected literature regarding the object of our study. This includes a systematic review of the literature, in order to understand the components of HRM and work related stress. The review helped us select important information, which is directly related to our study. The study is characterized by academic information and many practical analyses that can be easily understood by everyone. The information is gathered from different resources, including questionnaires filled in by the employees of Municipality of Korca. Later, this information is analysed using statistical and analytic methods, in order to get reliable conclusions. This methodology, based on facts and detailed analyses, makes our study valuable to the existing literature and the practices of HRM.

III. RESULTS

HRM is a base function, that gives an important contribute in achieving objectives, not only in the business field, but also in other aspects of human activity.

The main components that have been analysed in the study are recruitment, selection, training, development, compensation, performance appraisal and the management of employees' relationships.

HRM has the responsibility to create a healthy work environment, selection, development and appraisal mechanisms in order to reduce work related stress and improve the employees' wellbeing. This leads to higher productivity.

World Health Organisation considers work related stress to be a reaction of the employees when their abilities and knowledge do not match the requires and the pressure of the job, making it very challenging to face them. Health and Safety Executive, HSE, 2019 defines work related stress as an inappropriate reaction to pressure and extra duties. Other authors have given similar definitions. Topper (2007) said that

work-related stress is an outcome of the perception that one's ability does not match the requests of the environment (stress factors). Stress factors include different aspects of the work environment, which cause inappropriate reaction to stress, such as health of psychological problems (Glazer, S., & Beehr, T. A., 2005). Another definition of work related stress is given by Holmlund-Rytkönen & Strandvik, (2005). They define it as the inability to handle work pressure, because of a mismatch between one's ability and work requirements and environment.

Our study is focused on the effect of HRM in work related stress among employees of the Municipality of Korca. 280 employees took part in this study.

From all the people included in the study, 76% of them are females and 24% males. It is important to mention that a high number of women questioned can affect the way HR policies are perceived and implemented, especially regarding the balance between personal and professional life. The majority of responders are 25-40 years old (54%) and 38% are 40-55 years old. Only 8% are young that 25 and no one over 55. This shows that our study is focused on individuals on their most active years, when perception of stress and the expectations for personal and professional development are high. From the questionnaire, we can see that 70% of the responders are married and 30% single. Marital status can affect work related stress, because married individuals have different personal and family responsibilities, which may affect the way they handle work tasks.

Singles can have more flexibility, but they also might feel lonely on the workplace, which might be a stress factor. Also, the people included in the poll have different levels of education, with a majority of Master Degree (44%). The advanced education show that the employees have invested in their professional development and have high expectations for support and development opportunities from the organization. This factor can affect in the stress of the employees if the organization do not offer the right opportunities for further growth and development. The people included in the study have a divided experience, in which most of them worked for 5-10 years (43%), while a similar percentage worked 1-5 years or more than 10 years. From the study it results that the studied cases have this approach towards the human resources: The surveyed expressed a high level of consent for the recruiting and selection processes, with a majority that agree that the organization follows a clear and rigorous policy on this direction, Improving the recruitment and selection is crucial to minimize the stress at work, because the transparent and structured processes make the employees feel safer and more valued. The department of the human services follows rigorously the steps of the selection process and using the panel interview for the interviewing process increases its quality. The management is finding more and more that the training and perfecting the employees is one of the most effective ways of creating the competition priority. Our results show that most of the surveyed (49%), agree that the organization supports their training and development.

This is a key factor in reducing of stress, because the effective training (for new and existing employees), helps in preparing the employees for the work challenges and increasing their abilities, making them safer and more devoted. A value of the work of the department of the human resources is the periodic evaluation of the effect of the training in the results and the behavior of the employees. A positive fact is that 65% of the surveyed have an ambition for development and in 75% of the cases they are supported by the organization and in 49% of the cases, the leaders communicate in a transparent way career opportunities. Regardless agreeing for most of the aspects of the human resources, there is a considerable percentage of the employees who are neutral or not satisfied with the reward system (49%). The salary and the reward are important factors that affect the stress of the employees, and the competition with the private sector can be a challenge that should be addressed from the organization to keep the staff motivated. 33% of the surveyed agree that the reward system affect the performance in the work of the employees.

According to the gathered data from the questionnaire for the municipality of the circle of Korca, regardless the promising indicators connected with the management components of the human resources, most of the surveyed report that they feel sometimes stressed (57%) or rarely (24%), suggesting that stress is present, but not permanent. However, 16% report that they feel often stressed, that shows the need for a specific intervention from the organization to improve the support towards the stress at work.

Our study was focused also in the analyses of the personal and organizational factors, which affect stress. It results that the employees are in general satisfied with their work, where most of them think that the work is suitable for them and allows them to have a good work life balance. An interesting job and sufficient time to realize their duties are positive factors that help in reducing the personal stress.

About the work environment, most of the surveyed agree that the organization has created a proper physical environment for the work and to take care of the employee's mental health (73%). However, the salary is still a stressful issue for some, because it does not cover their needs, affecting their general perception on stability and financial security.

IV. CONCLUSION

From the studies considered on this paper, we can conclude that the changes in the components of the Management of the Human Resources have a tangible impact on the stress level of the employees. The right and transparent practices of recruitment and selection help in lowering the stress, while continuous training and development increase the confidence and the abilities of the employees, making them more stable towards the challenges in the workplace. Clear and fair compensation and reward policies play a crucial role in reducing the stress related to the performance and the rightfulness in the workplace. A supporting environment and good relationships between the employees and managers are necessary for the general wellbeing. Continuous improvement of these components of the MHR can reduce significantly the stress of the employees, contributing in a more productive and healthy work environment. This study confirmed that the changes well managed by the components of the Management of the Human Resources can affect in lowering the stress of the employees, improving their wellbeing and productivity. For the managers and policy makers, it is crucial to build clear and transparent MHR policies, ensuring a work environment that minimizes stress and supports the optimal performance of the employees.

The organizations should create and retain an open and supportive work environment, where the relationships between employees and management are healthy and based in open communication. The good relationships between managers and employees help in lowering the stress and improving the general wellbeing of the staff.

The organizations should create programs to monitor and manage the stress of the employees. This can include offering trainings for stress management, professional help in treating stressful situations, and programs for the general wellbeing of the staff. An environment which relays on tools and programs for managing stress, helps in lowering fatigue and chronic stress.

Organizations should encourage the participation of the employees in the decision-making processes. The employees who feel included in decisions are less likely to experience stress, because they feel evaluated and more connected with the organizational processes.

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